

Treatment of Nocturnal Enuresis using Yoga Prana Vidya Healing Protocols: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Nocturnal enuresis, is night-time bedwetting in children five years of age or older, and is a common but disturbing condition causing psychological distress in affected children. Though not considered as a serious health problem, several treatment options are available. This paper presents a case of Nocturnal enuresis suffered by a 7-year-old boy who was successfully treated using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Protocols.

Method: Case study method is used in the analysis of this case, by collecting data from patient medical records, healer's records and patient's parent feedback.

Results: Within 14 days of YPV healing by the healer, gradually the frequency of urine pass at night sleep reduced. Also, it was found during follow up that the patient completely recovered and cured of this condition, and because of the holistic healing properties of YPV system and regular self- practices such as rhythmic breathing, forgiveness sadhana and Super-brain Asana, the patient grew up to be a normally healthy teenager without any health issues.

Conclusions: Integrated and holistic healing properties of YPV system protocols have been helping thousands of people to overcome physical, mental and emotional issues with sustained results when practiced consistently. Further research on this topic using appropriate methodology and sample size is recommended. It will be highly beneficial for all frontline healthcare workers such as doctors and nurses to acquire a working knowledge of YPV healing practices in combination with their respective specialties to holistically treat patients for sustainable results of cure.

KEYWORDS: Nocturnal enuresis, Bedwetting, Yoga Prana Vidya System®, YPV®

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INTRODUCTION

Nocturnal enuresis is defined as night-time bedwetting in children five years of age or older [1], and is a common condition that can cause substantial psychological distress in children with the condition. It is not considered as a serious health problem, yet bedwetting can be upsetting for children and parents. It is advisable to consult child's doctors to find possible causes and solutions. [1]

The worldwide prevalence of enuresis among children aged 6–12 years is 1.4%–28%. Data on incidence and prevalence in India are very limited. In general, prevalence of nocturnal enuresis is higher among male children than female children. The prevalence in India is 7.61%–16.3%. The prevalence is highest in children aged 5–8 years (and 6–8 years) and lowest in children aged 11–12 years (8–10 years). Nocturnal enuresis

has been reported in 18.4% of children with sleep problems from a single center in India.[2]

Nocturnal enuresis can be classified as primary enuresis is when a child has never had bladder control at night and has always wet the bed, and secondary enuresis is when a child did have bladder control at night for a period of at least 6 months, but lost that control and now wets the bed again. Secondary enuresis in older children or teens should be evaluated by a doctor. Bedwetting in this age group could be a sign of a urinary tract infection or other health problems, neurological issues, stress, or other issues.

Although the reason for bedwetting is not completely understood, it is thought to happen because of a delay in the development of Bladder (less space in the bladder at night),

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increased Kidney function (more urine is made at night) and brain unable to wake up during sleep.

The other factors for bedwetting could be genetics, stress, deep sleep, obstructive sleep apnea/snoring, constipation, bladder or kidney disease and neurologic disease. Bedwetting may have an emotional impact on both children and their families. Children may get embarrassed, feel anxious, or develop low self-esteem. This can affect their relationships, quality of life, and schoolwork. Children with bedwetting may feel like they cannot go to sleepovers with their friends or overnight camps. Siblings may have to sleep in separate rooms or be woken up when the parent or bedwetting alarm wakes the affected child. Family members may have the extra work of cleaning the dirty sheets and clothes. It is very important to understand that bedwetting is not the child's fault nor under his or her control.

Simple urine test shows signs of a disease or an infection. In most children with enuresis, the results of this test come back completely normal. Treatment for bedwetting first depends on if it is due to stress, that needs to be managed first. Comorbid conditions that can cause or contribute to enuresis should be identified and managed, because the child's response to management may be impaired if other conditions are untreated. In case of constipation, it should be treated because enuresis may resolve spontaneously afterwards.

Pharmacotherapy should be limited to children seven years or older, and can be used if initial nonpharmacologic therapy is unsuccessful or if families prefer medications as initial therapy. Medications are more convenient than behavioural or alarm therapy, but symptoms typically return after discontinuation. [3]

This paper presents a case of nocturnal enuresis that comes under category of primary, monosymptomatic condition, and treated using Yoga Prana Vidya healing protocols by an experienced YPV healer.

YOGA PRANA VIDYA SYSTEM

The broad concept of Yoga has to be viewed and understood, while Yoga in recent times is being used only to refer to Asanas or postures of physical exercises and sometimes even to pranayama or a form of systematic breathing exercise. These Yoga postures are in fact parts of Yoga and not the complete Yoga. Yoga as propounded by Yogi Patanjali, is actually known as Ashtanga Yoga consisting of 8 steps and each of the steps is equally very important. There are many levels of Yoga in practice. As per the ancient Yogic teachings, the physical body is an important vehicle of the Soul for use in the physical world and it must be maintained, sustained and used for the purpose of the Divine plan on earth. The purpose of yoga is to achieve union of the soul with the Divine and manifest its greatness on Earth. Mind itself is the instrument of the Soul. In addition to treating the physical body, it is also important to maintain healthy state of the energy body (also known as etheric body) in order to sustain, maintain or regain good health. Anything that happens to the physical body, also affects the Etheric Body and vice versa. The Prana is Life Force or Energy used for the maintenance of the energy body and Vidya is the know-how. The technology of maintaining the energy body is therefore termed Yoga Prana Vidya (or YPV) system which offers integrated and holistic techniques for maintaining both physical and energy bodies and also maintain the etheric connectivity with the higher self. Healing is the process by which the energy body can be renewed thus bringing beneficial changes in the physical body. Used up energy or diseased energy can be removed and the energy body can be charged with fresh energy. All biological life on earth has the ability to heal itself. Energy follows thought and energy accelerates the healing process. Healing involves two steps: (1) Cleansing, or removing the used-up energy and (2) Energizing, or giving fresh energy. In YPV, the healer thus becomes a channel of energy, who receives and transfers energy (See figure 1).

Figure 1. Channelling Pranic Energy

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) is a revolutionary form of energy "medicine". It is based on ancient science and art that has

been revived in a new form which is easily adaptable and is compatible with busy life in modern world. A healer can heal

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him/herself besides healing others. There are two modes of YPV healing. In one mode, a healer heals the other person who is seated facing the healer in the same room, which is known as proximal healing. In the other mode known as distal healing, a healer is situated at a place away from the patient, and healing energy can be sent distantly and instantly through inter-connection with and through the earth's energy body. During pandemic times such as COVID, distal healing had been effectively the main mode used to deliver healing energies to all needed patients situated hundreds or even thousands of kilometres away. It is an integrated, no-drug and no-touch healing modality and can be used as alternative or complimentary to other treatment methods.

A search of the literature shows that, by using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing techniques, many cases have been successfully treated such as, some difficult medical cases, Diabetes management & control, removing arterial block in heart without surgery, vision improvements for participants of an Eye Camp, improvements in holistic wellbeing and immunity of participants in a one-month YPV intensive programme, Role of Yoga Prana Vidya in first aid and emergency, improvements of health and immunity of senior citizens, speedy recovery of COVID patients, treatment of hypothyroidism, Lowering academic anxiety and enhancing academic performance of high school children, saving life of a snake-bitten human female, improvements in the cognitive abilities and social behaviour of mentally challenged children, managing the pain and side effects of a Hodgkin Lymphoma patient undergoing chemotherapy, healing treatment of a female patient suffering from kneecap dislocation [4-17]. A review of published literature shows some experimental studies also conducted with successful outcomes such as improvements in the wellbeing of prisoners [18], and significant reduction in anxiety and depression in corporate employees [19].

The authors are presenting a case report of a boy of 7 years age suffering from nocturnal enuresis, treated successfully using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) protocols as alternative therapy

CASE REPORT

Patient details

The patient was a 7 years old boy living with his parents in Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Patient condition before YPV Healing

During October, 2014, the mother of the subject 7yr old boy residing in Mangalore consulted a YPV healer and requested to heal her son who was suffering from nocturnal enuresis. Normally children stop bedwetting at night at the age of 2-3yrs, but this boy did not. She waited till the age of 5 and she reminding him every night to pass urine before sleeping and advised him to avoid drinking water or liquid items at the evening and night, but no improvement happened even till the age of 7. Then she consulted YPV healer through her friend.

After YPV Healing

Healer started healing on 10th Oct2014 once a day before sleeping for 15min and also advised to do breathing exercise 3 times daily and super brain asana once a day. Stress and fear energies were removed using light whitish violet prana from his energy body. Affected chakrams, viz., sex chakram and related organs cleansed and energised with white prana. Remaining chakrams cleansed and balanced. Organs like kidney, lungs and spleen are also cleansed. Day by day gradually the frequency of urine pass at night during sleep reduced. He completely recovered within 2 weeks of distant healings (by 24 October, 2014). Mother and son were happy and he did not have any health issues subsequently. He continued breathing exercise and super-brain asana.

Follow up

When he had grown up, he developed interest in learning YPV healing and he was practicing breathing exercise, forgiveness sadhana, and super-brain asana. He is very talented active intelligent boy in studies and also participates insinging, dancing, karate and also in cooking activities. He continued YPV practices and now he is 16yr old learnt YPV healing and practicing.

Feedback from patient's mother

"Usually, children attain their bladder control at night at the age of 2-3yrs, but he did not. I waited till the age of 5yrs, and then I started reminding him daily to empty bladder urine just before go to the bed, and also advised him to avoid drinking water and liquid in the evenings and at night, and also I tried to wake him up in between the sleep at night, but still it did not work till the age of 7."

"One of my friends told me to consult a YPV healer, I consulted and took Healings for about 2weeks. She also advised to do breathing exercises 3 times a day and sit-ups (super brain asana) before sleeping. After that gradually he decreased the number of urine pass at night during sleep and stopped eventually. Thanks to YPV and healer."

DISCUSSION

A search of literature shows scanty literature on the treatment of nocturnal enuresis using Pranic energy and this case article is perhaps the first of its kind. However, the use of various other complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) treatments in children is increasing. Due to the ineffectiveness of some pharmacological interventions or intolerance to their side effects, different types of CAM are used in various problems, such as enuresis in children. [20]

A study by Saha et al. (2018) concluded that Homoeopathic medicines seemed to have a potential treatment effect in nocturnal enuresis. [21] In another study, Radhamohan et al (2019) found that, both behavioural therapy as well as imipramine show better results when combined together rather than given alone. [22] Despite the relatively high use of CAM treatments in nocturnal enuresis among children, evidence of their effectiveness is not adequately reported.

CONCLUSION

More clinical trials are recommended to evaluate the safety and efficacy of various CAM methods. The applications of Yoga Prana Vidya protocols, with their role as complementary or alternative to the mainstream medical systems, to heal and treat various illness conditions successfully, have been established very well as evidenced in published literature. This case study results are suggestive of great scope YPV offers to treat nocturnal enuresis as an effective holistic alternative treatment modality, and it is worth investigating with further research using appropriate methodology and sample size. An insight this case offers is to consider imparting a working knowledge of YPV protocols to frontline healthcare workers such as practicing doctors and nurses with a view to complementing their respective specialties to holistically treat patients for sustained results.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

None

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